

Hydrogen Bonding Induced Solid State Supramolecular Assemblies of Selective *O*-Tosyl and *N*-Tosyl Derivatives of 3-Aminophenol[†]

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Self-organisation via hydrogen bonding in the supramolecular assembly of selective mono-tosyl derivative of 3-aminophenol having free amino group (1) and free hydroxyl group (2) respectively, has been demonstrated. Compound 1 is stabilised in the solid state forming a sixteen-membered hydrogen bonded structure in the self-assembly and compound 2 forms a column like structure with alternate different grooves.

Self-organisation in supramolecular assembly¹ is the process by which small molecular components² spontaneously assemble in a highly selective fashion into a well defined, discrete supramolecular architecture³. For its success, hydrogen bonds⁴ have been widely used for the development of synthetic receptors⁵ and for the design of supramolecular crystals⁶ because of their strength as well as directional nature relative to the other intermolecular non-covalent interactions. Our goal in this work was to develop simple chemical analogues of self-assembly in solid state crystal sheet. All these assemblies involve hydrogen bonding induced recognition process in self-organisation. We were interested in the X-ray studies of the tosyl derivatives since these compounds specially sulfonamides (*N*-tosyl) are known to have important biological activities⁷. Sulfonamides have been extensively used against many common gram-positive bacteria infections like pneumonia, meningitis, dysentery and urinary tract infections⁸. *O*-Tosyl moiety may be biologically active to mimic the enzyme activities in the living organism.

Results and Discussion

Selective derivatives of 3-aminophenol, i.e. *O*-tosyl (1) and *N*-tosyl (2) form supramolecular self-assembly in the solid state crystal sheet through hydrogen bonding. Both *O*-tosyl and *N*-tosyl adopt monoclinic crystal type and number of molecules per unit cell is 4 and 8 respectively.

X-ray structure analysis :

Crystal structure of compound 1 (Fig. 1a, b and c) is stabilised by N-H---O intermolecular hydrogen bonds involving amino and sulphonyloxy oxygen atoms. In hydrogen bonding network of the crystal sheet shows that sixteen-membered hydrogen bonded cyclic structure with al-

ternate tolyl-methyl down and up along *b*-axis (Fig. 1b).

The planar amino group is twisted by 9 (2)^o from tolyl sulphonyloxy moieties. The dihedral angle between the toluene and aniline moieties is 64.26 (5)^o. The SI-O2, SI-O3, SI-O1, N1-C1 and mean value of C-C distances [1.381 (3) Å] agree with the reported values⁹.

Fig. 1a. ORTEP diagram of 1 (showing 50% probability displacement).

In the crystal structure of compound 2 (Fig. 2a and 2b) the tosyl-amino group and the hydroxyl group involve in N-H---O and O-H---O intermolecular hydrogen bonds to assemble the molecules in a column like structure along *b*-axis (Fig. 2b).

The molecules translated one unit cell along the *b*-direction are linked by O-H---O intermolecular hydrogen bonds

Fig. 1b. Hydrogen bonding network of 1.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Fig. 1c. Hydrogen bonding network of (zig-zag) of 1 down *c*-axis.

involving the hydroxyl group and sulfonamide oxygen atom, to form a chain. The dihedral angle between the toluene and phenol moieties is 69.48 (5)°. The S atom adopts each in a tetrahedral coordination. The sum of the bond angles around N1 [349 (1)°] indicates that it is in a pyramidal configuration. The S–O, N–C and mean value of C–C distances agree with the reported values⁹. The phenol groups occupy a plane and the toluene groups project outwards from it on either side to create grooves.

Fig. 2a. ORTEP diagram of 2 (showing 50% probability displacement).

Fig. 2b. Hydrogen bonding network of 2.

TABLE 1—CRYSTAL DATA AND STRUCTURE REFINEMENT FOR COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2

	Compd. 1	Compd. 2
Empirical formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₃ S	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₃ S
Formula weight	263.30	263.30
Wave length, Å	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal habit	rectangular	block
Crystal system	monoclinic	monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>	<i>C</i> 2/ <i>c</i>
Unit cell dimensions (a)		
<i>a</i>	9.9807 (7)	23.9096 (7)
<i>b</i>	7.5585 (6)	9.5192 (3)
<i>c</i>	17.0244 (12)	11.9629 (3)
β	90.196 (7)°	112.136 (1)°
Volume (Å ³)	1284.3 (2)	2522.07 (13)
<i>Z</i>	4	8
Density (calculated)	1.362 Mg m ⁻³	1.387 Mg m ⁻³
Reflections collected	3939	8060
Independent reflections	2930	2898
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 sigma (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> ₁ =0.0386 <i>wR</i> ² =0.1074	<i>R</i> ₁ =0.0364 <i>wR</i> ² =0.1020
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.266 and -0.211 eÅ ⁻³	0.218 and 0.280 eÅ ⁻³

TABLE 2—HYDROGEN BONDING PARAMETERS (Å, DEG)

Compd. 1 :				
D—H...A	D—H	H...A	D...A	D—H...A
C8—H8...O2	0.96 (2)	2.47 (2)	2.901 (2)	107 (1)
N1—H1N1...O3 ⁱ	0.81 (2)	2.31 (2)	3.098 (3)	165 (2)
N1—H2N1...O2 ⁱⁱ	0.79 (3)	2.52 (3)	3.278 (3)	162 (2)
Compd. 2 :				
D—H...A	D—H	H...A	D...A	D—H...A
O1—H1...O3 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.79 (3)	1.95 (3)	2.727 (2)	171 (2)
N1—H1N1...O1 ^{iv}	0.85 (2)	2.14 (2)	2.983 (2)	174 (2)
Symmetry codes : (i) <i>x</i> , + 1/2 - <i>y</i> , <i>z</i> - 1/2; (ii) 1 - <i>x</i> , - <i>y</i> , 1 - <i>z</i> ; (iii) <i>x</i> , 1 + <i>y</i> , <i>z</i> ; (iv) 1/2 - <i>x</i> , <i>y</i> - 1/2, 1/2 - <i>z</i> .				

TABLE 3—SELECTED BOND LENGTHS AND BOND ANGLES OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2

Compd. 1 :			
S1—O2	1.4214 (15)	S1—C7	1.756 (2)
S1—O3	1.4232 (14)	O1—C5	1.431 (2)
S1—O1	1.584 (2)	N1—C1	1.365 (3)
Compd. 2 :			
S—O2	1.4259 (13)	S—C7	1.760 (2)
S—O3	1.4347 (12)	O1—C1	1.371 (2)
S—N1	1.6214 (13)	N1—C5	1.432 (2)
O2—S—O3	119.55 (8)	O3—S—C7	107.62 (8)
O2—S—N1	108.65 (8)	N1—S—C7	107.96 (7)
O3—S—N1	104.59 (7)	C5—N1—S	123.62 (11)
O2—S—C7	107.97 (8)		

In conclusion, the crystal structures of two simple monotosyl derivatives of 3-aminophenol having *O*-tosyl with free aromatic NH₂ group (1) and *N*-tosyl with free aromatic OH group (2) demonstrate that different hydrogen bonding groups form interesting different supramolecular assembly in the self-organisation in the solid state. Compound 1 having free amino group self-organises to stabilise itself to form a sixteen-membered intermolecular hydrogen bonded cyclic structure where NH donates hydrogen bond to sulphonyloxy oxygen. In compound 2 with free phenolic OH group forms hydrogen bond with oxygen of sulfonamide group along with NH hydrogen bond with oxygen of sulfonamide moiety resulting a column like structure (Fig. 2b). Interestingly, tolyl groups of the neighbouring columns are closely positioned but are not stacked to have π - π interaction.

Crystal data, hydrogen bonding parameters, and bond length and bond angles of compounds 1 and 2 are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Experimental

m-(*p*-Tolylsulphonyloxy)aniline (1) : *p*-Toluene-sulphonyl chloride (1 equivalent) was added to a solution in dry dichloromethane containing 3-aminophenol (1 equivalent) and triethylamine (1 equivalent) at 0°. Reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min at 0° and another 45 min at room temperature. After usual work-up it gave the desired compound in 90% yield.

Single crystals were grown by slow evaporation of 1 : 1 dichloromethane and petroleum ether solution of the compound.

m-(*p*-Tolylsulphonamide)phenol (2) : *p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (1 equivalent) was added to a solution in dry dichloromethane containing 3-aminophenol (1 equivalent) and pyridine (1 equivalent) at 10°. Reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min and another 1 h at room temperature. It gave the desired product in 80% yield after the usual work-up.

Single crystals were grown by slow evaporation of 4 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and methanol of the solution of the compound.

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Note : Data were collected on a SMART CCD area detector using graphite monochromated MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). Collected data were reduced by using the program SAINT (G. M. Sheldrick, SAINT v4 Software Reference Manual, Siemens Analytical X-ray Systems, Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA, 1996). The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by least-squares on F_{obs}^2 by using the SHELXTL (G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXTL v5 Software Reference Manual, Siemens Analytical X-ray Systems, Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA 1996). Supplementary data (thermal parameters, atomic coordinates, bond lengths, bond angle) for this paper are available from the principal author.